

AN OPTIMIZED AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED TASK SCHEDULING IN PARALLEL CLOUD COMPUTINGHema Yadav^{*1}
Lalit bansal²^{*1} M.Tech (Scholar), Department of Computer Science and Engineering Guru Nanak Institutions, Mullana² Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering Guru Nanak Institutions, Mullana
hemayadav39@gmail.com,
lalit.cse@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

In parallel computing, scheduling can be defined as a collection of laws in which execution order has been defined in detailed manner. To perform scheduling in parallel computing, multiprocessor is utilized and it required to arranging the resources for all processors. The problem of task scheduling can be utilized to finding or, searching the best allocation of distinguished task from available resources such as processors, computers to obtain desired aim. Task scheduling and managing the resources is the main challenge of parallel computing to resolve this issue, in this proposed work the DAG (Directed Acyclic graph) is used. To optimize the resources and scheduling of task better here the optimization algorithm is utilized named as Cuckoo Search (CS). After get the optimized task for classification purpose the neural network i.e. Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is applied here, by which it's easy to allocation of resources to processes.

Keywords:

Parallel Computing, CS, ANN, Task Scheduling, DAG.

INTRODUCTION

In parallel computing, enormous processors needs to be scheduled and its necessary to manage the resources for the entire task, it should be ensured that there is no any overlapping of the resources and it should not give any conflicting results [1]. In scheduling of multiprocessors it should be sure about the processors is not over-loaded or, under –loaded, so the overall system must be balanced [2]

Multiprocessor Computing Systems

A multiprocessor is a computer system having two or more CPUs (central processing units), each sharing a common basic memory and peripherals [3]. In multiprocessor computing, the problem is divided into different sub parts that might be solved simultaneously as shown in figure below:

Fig. 1: Multiprocessor Computing

A good example of multiprocessor is a single central tower connected to two computer systems. This kind of systems beat the systems that performs in sequential manner by using the shared memory and it also composed of own locally available memory which is not useful for other processors.

Task Scheduling

Scheduling in single processor is easy as compare to the scheduling in multiprocessor. The task scheduling problem can be used as finding or, searching the best allocation of distinguished task from available resources such as processors, computers to obtain desired aim. In this proposed work the DAG (Directed Acyclic graph) is used to achieve better scheduling [4]. The detailed working of DAG model is explained below: In a depicted graph, a task having no any precedence is known as the input task and it denoted as t_{input} and a node or task without any successors is termed as an exit task and denoted as t_{exit} .

Fig. 2: DAG Model [4]

The graph is represents as $G(a, b)$, where, a is the number of vertices and b is the number of edge. As shown in the fig. 2 single arrow represents a child node whereas the multiple arrows represent the parent's node. For an example, node t_8 has three parents named as t_2 , t_4 and t_6 .

RELATED WORK

In this section, some existing works related to our proposed work has been discussed. Along with the optimization algorithm i.e. Cuckoo search is used to optimize the resources for allocation among processes. And also the classification algorithms that are utilized previously by a number of researchers for task scheduling in the parallel computing has been gathered here. The classification algorithm is utilized to collect data from different networks and train the system on the basis of extracted and optimized features of data.

Yue et al. (2019) presented a parallel strategy in which the entire computing of the distributed hydrological model is divided into incredible amount of small sub-tasks that are dispatched directly into the nodes of cluster through the traditional local resource managers (LRMs). The scheme of task- splitting, task model with single processor and the representation of

dependencies among tasks are also presented. To schedule the various tasks in effective manner, a dynamic DAG scheduling scheme on the basis of critical path and depth is provided.

Juarez et al. (2018) proposed a real-time adaptive scheduling system to effectively deploy task-based applications on distributed computing frameworks to reduce energy consumption. The proposed algorithm minimizes a multi-objective function that combines energy-consumption and runtime based on the energy-performance-importance parameter provided or used by the resource provider. In addition, they also measured the overhead added by calculating the time required for scheduling solutions for a variety of tasks, types of DAG, and resources.

Laha, D., & Gupta, J. N. (2018) presented an improved cuckoo search algorithm (ICSA) to reduce make span for the identical parallel machine scheduling algorithm. Initiate with an initial population of methods produces through the longest processing time (LPT) rule and the job- interchange method. Best scheduled is selected from the population and execute this proposed ICSA. First, suggest a heuristic method using a module operator to transform a continuous CSA position into a discrete schedule of jobs for Levy flights to generate a new cuckoo. Next, in the proposed ICSA, presented a heuristic procedure based on the neighborhood for pair exchange to produce smart cuckoos.

Tchórzewski et al. (2018) proposed an intelligent system to support security services in Computational Clouds (CC) that involves two distinguished types of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and an evolutionary algorithm. The scheduler regards the features of tasks in terms of the requirements of size and security. This system takes into account the sorting incoming batches of tasks according to their privacy requirements. This allows one to divide the traffic into streams which is executed through distinguished kinds of the CC environment. Here, in this work utilizes the classifier or, sorter ANN to execute the task scheduling.

Agrawal et al. (2017) presented an active scheduling method for multiprocessor unit time tasks with chain priority over a large multiprocessor network, the splitable and non-splitable multiprocessor tasks have been considered here. Having utilized three assumptions (i) maximum criticality at beginning (ii) expanded chain critical highly first and (iii) chain with longest length having maximum processor first for scheduling of uninformed chains.

Maurya, A. K., & Tripathi, A. K. (2018) investigated the task scheduling problem on heterogeneous computing systems. They have taken care of the comparison and evaluation of performance for task scheduling algorithms in heterogeneous computing systems. Investigate the possibility of a benchmarking method for heterogeneous computing process task scheduling algorithms. This introduced approach that allows the production of graphs via a Directed Acyclic Graph Generator, and then develops schedules.

Methodology

This section comprises the flow of presented work, in which, the work has been carried out along with the detail description of techniques used. The task scheduling on processors has been performed through DAG model and it has been presented on the basis of optimization algorithm such as Cuckoo search and classify the task through Artificial Neural Network (ANN). To perform scheduling on the processors by which it becomes easy to assign resources to processes.

Proposed Work

Initially number of processors along with the number of jobs, then DAG model along with the vertices a and edges b has been defined. Determine the parent and child node and calculate the communication and computation cost. The cost of computation is achieved by communication cost and computation cost combined, verify the parameters such as computation, energy consumption etc.

Fig. 3: Layered Architecture of ANN

The process is repeated until the desired cost is achieved. If the performance of the system is degraded then apply cuckoo search algorithm to optimize the task. After obtain the optimized task for processes then the next step is allocation; of these resources to the task. To observe which resource is assigned to the processes first by classification technique named as Artificial Neural Network.

Fig. 3 depicts the layered architecture of ANN that mainly includes input, hidden and output layer layers mainly. And shown the way neurons are linked with others have an impact on the operation of ANN. The algorithm of ANN is discussed.

Initially, all the processes are sorted on descending order according to priority of task. If there is more than one task with the same priority, then perform sorting on ascending order.

1. $n_t \rightarrow$ number of tasks
2. $s_t \rightarrow$ sum of tasks
3. $s_{pt} \rightarrow$ sum of tasks priorities
4. Perform normalization

Then, Artificial Neural Network has been loaded and predicts the accurate time interval for each task.

5. Get (i) \rightarrow predicted classification through Artificial Neural Network
6. $TQ \rightarrow$ Assigned time to processes

After that allocate the time to every submitted task ($b_t[j] = b_t[j] - TQ$)

7. For $j = 1$ to n_t
 $(b_t[j]) = b_t[j] - TQ$
 If $b_t[j] = 0$
 Send task to finish list

Else

Send task to waiting list

At the end, retrieve task on the waiting list and send them to ready list and compute the TQ dynamically for task on the new list,

8. Go to step 5
9. Continue until all tasks are finished.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section the outcome of the proposed work i.e. task scheduling on multiprocessor system has been discussed on the basis of parameters such as EFE (Earliest Finishing Energy) and ESE (Earliest Starting Energy). In task scheduling the allocation of resources to the processor (p) is the main aim its hard to see in the multiprocessor system. Since, in multiprocessor system various processors or, tasks are available to wait for the utilization of resources while at the same time the resource is consumed by another process.

Used platform

To perform the task scheduling as our proposed work, to run the codes java programming language is used on the platform of Net-Beans.

- Java Development Kit (JDK)

The Java Development Kit (JDK) is a software development kit used for developing Java applications and applets. It includes the Java Runtime Environment (JRE), an interpreter or a Java loader, a compiler i.e. javac, an archiver often called jar, a file generator i.e. javadoc, and other tools needed for Java development.

- Net-Beans

The NetBeans Framework allows the developer to develop its applications using modules. The framework is written in Java and has a set of tools. Net-Beans started as a student project named Xelfi in 1996 with the goal of writing a Java IDE "Delphi-like" in Java. Later Sun Microsystems decided to open it in 2000.

The parameters utilized here to compute the outcomes are discussed:

- i. Energy Consumption

For an active server, the total energy consumption for some provided time frame is the sum of energy consumed when the system dynamic and fixed. There is a generation of additional energy being generated that can be depicted by E_{Sched} . This let the energy consumption as of two tasks, which are not equal to the sum of individual consumed energy.

- ii. ESE (Earliest Start Energy)

This term in task scheduling is computed as moving forward through the nodes i.e. from start node to exit node on which task can commence by taking care of its predecessor nodes.

- iii. EFE (Earliest Finish Energy)

This energy is computed using the expected energy for the required allocation of resources to the processors. It is mainly determined by moving forward to the nodes and obtained earliest energy at which an activity has finished by considering its predecessor performance.

In the figure 4 shows the earliest finish energy of nodes for allocation of resources to the task. Here, the obtained EFE and ESE as depict in figure 6.1 of graphical form in which 10 number of nodes represented corresponds to x-axis and produced EFE is represented corresponds to the y-axis. The number of nodes varies from N0 to N9, corresponds to this nodes the obtained EFE is varying from 0-700 without any scheduling algorithm has been utilized here. As the number of nodes increase corresponds to this the EFE is not incremented so this graph is non-linear. As we can see the lowest EFE is 150 and highest EFE is 675, to represent the distinguished nodes different colors are used for example node 1 is represented by light blue color and node 3 is represented by yellow color by which it's easy to see the differentiate the nodes.

Fig. 4: EFE (Earliest Finish Energy) Consumption

In the above Table 1 the ESE and EFE is depicted corresponds to the 10 number of nodes, the initial node starts at zero earliest start energy this nodes stops execution after reached at the earliest finish energy 210. The highest EFE is produced by the node 7 i.e. 685 and lowest energy consumed by the node 9 i.e. 55.

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TABLE 1: EFE CONSUMPTION

No. of Nodes	ESE (Earliest Start Energy)	EFE (Earliest Finish Energy)
1	0	201
2	18	118
3	12	116
4	116	256
5	256	414
6	132	312
7	312	452
8	427	497
9	214	55
10	465	685

The execution of next node is not depends on the completion of execution of previous nodes it can be start to execute. The average energy consumption without apply any algorithm applies have obtained 31.06%. In the next figure after applied Cuckoo search and ANN.

Fig. 5: EFE with cuckoo and neural

In fig. 5 discuss the consumption of energy with utilizing optimization and classification algorithm such as Cuckoo search (CS) by which it's easy to allocate the resources to processes. After optimization to see which task is assigned to processor apply

classification named as Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The graph of EFE is plotted corresponds to the y-axis against the number of 10 numbers of nodes as corresponds to the x-axis and stat from 0 to 9, as depicted in the diagram the consumed earliest finish energy is lower than previous one. Since here we applied the optimization algorithm to optimize the resources to allocate it among processes. Here, also the color of nodes is different by which one node is easily distinguished from other nodes.

Table 2: EFE Consumption using Cuckoo and Neural

No. of Nodes	ESE (Earliest Start Energy)	EFE (Earliest Finish Energy)
1	0	180
2	18	100
3	12	29
4	116	100
5	256	302
6	132	300
7	312	309
8	427	395
9	214	307
10	465	525

In the Table 2 the algorithm Cuckoo search and ANN has been applied on the task to allocate it among resources and analyze the consumption of energy i.e. ESE and EFE has been reduced as compare to the without applied any algorithm. The reduced EFE is 25.47% and it reduces by the amount of 6% in same number of nodes and the ESE is also same. Therefore, it has to be concluded that this proposed work consumed less energy in allocation of resources to task by applying the DAG algorithm and so its performance is better.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we discussed the concluded findings of this proposed work. The task scheduling problem can be used as finding or, searching the best allocation of distinguished task from available resources such as processors, computers to obtain desired aim. Task scheduling and managing the resources is the main challenge of parallel computing to resolve this issue, in this proposed work the DAG (Directed Acyclic graph) is used to achieve better scheduling. After the process of resource allocation and utilization through the DAG model by using HEFT(Heterogeneous Earliest Finish Time), CPOP(Critical Path On Processor) and DVFS(Dynamic Voltage Frequency Scaling). To optimize the resources better and scheduling of task, here the optimization algorithm is utilized named as Cuckoo Search (CS). After obtained, at the end it has to classify them by using neural network i.e. Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is utilized here mainly in the layered manner. From the simulation work, it has been analyzed that DVFS has performed well and has reduced energy consumption value by 6%.

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